

Comparison of Collum Angle of Maxillary Central Incisor in Vertical and Horizontal growers in Central Indian Population: A cross sectional study

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ABSTRACT-

Introduction: Orthodontic treatment is often sought due to aesthetic concerns like malalignment of upper central incisors, which affects facial appearance. The collum angle (CA), which measures the relationship between the crown and root, is crucial in orthodontics, particularly for the maxillary central incisors. Variations in this angle can influence tooth movement and the outcomes of procedures like intrusion and extrusion.

Objective: The study aimed to assess and compare the collum angle of the maxillary central incisor in patients with vertical and horizontal growth patterns undergoing orthodontic treatment.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study used lateral cephalograms from 100 patients (52 males and 48 females, ages 13-30) with Class II Division 1 malocclusion. Patients were categorized based on their mandibular plane angles into vertical and horizontal growth patterns groups. The collum angle was measured and analyzed using a t-test to compare the results.

Results: The mean collum angle for vertical growers was $4.35^{\circ} \pm 1.49^{\circ}$, while it was $2.41^{\circ} \pm 1.60^{\circ}$ for horizontal growers. The study found a significant difference between the two groups ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: There is a notable difference in the collum angle between vertical and horizontal growth patterns, with higher axial bending seen in vertical growth cases. These variations play an important role in treatment planning to avoid complications such as root resorption and improper bracket positioning.

Keywords: Collum angle, Vertical growth pattern, Horizontal growth pattern, Maxillary Central Incisor, Central India.

INTRODUCTION-

Smile aesthetics, facial appearance, and social interactions are key reasons people seek orthodontic treatment.^{1,2} The upper central incisors are the most noticeable teeth during typical facial expressions. Significant misalignment of these teeth negatively impacts facial aesthetics, lip closure, and proper occlusion. Even slight misalignments often concern patients.³

Each tooth's shape is determined by factors like crown width, height, and angulation, all of which are heavily influenced by genetics.⁴ The angle between the crown and root, known as the collum angle (CA), is crucial in orthodontics, particularly for upper central incisors, and plays an important role in planning tooth movement.^{5,6} Proper occlusion of the front teeth is essential to resolve aesthetic issues, which is dependent on the labial and lingual positioning of the incisors. The crown-to-root angulation also dictates how much the maxillary central incisors should be torqued to avoid perforating the buccal or lingual cortical plates.³ Studies have shown that variations in root angulation can lead to unwanted force application during tooth movements like intrusion and extrusion.⁷

As the collum angle increases, the intrusion of the tooth into the alveolar bone decreases, as the centre of rotation shifts downward, closer to the tooth cervix, causing more strain in the periodontal ligament.⁸ While several studies have shown differences in CA between various malocclusion types and between high and low angle cases, there is limited research on this subject in our population. Earlier research using CBCT and CT techniques provided valuable insights,^{3,6} but cephalometric radiography has also proven effective in yielding more accurate results.^{4,7}

This study aimed to compare the collum angle of upper central incisors in patients with different vertical malocclusions using lateral cephalograms. While the collum angle has been extensively studied in sagittal malocclusions, there has been limited focus on vertical malocclusion in this population. Knowledge of the collum angle's impact on torque variation,

root resorption, and other dental issues will allow orthodontists to better manage high and low angle cases and optimize bracket positioning in future treatments.

METHODOLOGY-

The research was a cross-sectional observational study conducted at the Department of Orthodontics, Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur, Maharashtra. The study involved analysing lateral cephalometric radiographs of 100 patients with Class II Division 1 malocclusion and was carried out between January and April 2023. The sample size was determined using the WHO sample size calculator.

$$\left(n = \frac{z^2 \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \sigma^2}{d^2} \text{ or } \frac{z^2 \frac{1-\alpha}{2} \sigma^2}{\epsilon^2 \mu^2} \right).$$

Patients were categorized into vertical growers (n=50) and horizontal growers (n=50) based on the SNMP angle obtained from their lateral cephalograms. Consecutive sampling was used to select the patients, with both genders represented in the age range of 13 to 30 years seeking orthodontic treatment and having Class II Division 1 malocclusion. To accurately measure the collum angle of the maxillary central incisors on the lateral cephalometric radiographs, it was crucial for researchers to identify the natural tooth axis. As a result, patients with prostheses (such as posts, dental implants, or fixed partial dentures) in the anterior region were excluded from the study. Additionally, radiographs that showed severe crowding or mixed dentition in the anterior region were not included in the analysis. Exclusion criteria also included patients with supernumerary teeth, hypodontia, craniofacial syndromes, poor incisor visibility, incisor rotations, a history of surgery, or poor-quality radiographs.

A single calibrated examiner traced and measured all points and angles on the cephalometric radiographs. The patients were divided into vertical and horizontal growers based on specific SNMP, FHMP, and MMA values (SN-MP > 37°, FH-MP > 30°, MMA > 28° for vertical growers; SN-MP < 28°, FH-MP < 21°, MMA < 21° for horizontal growers). The collum angle was then measured for each patient.

Collum Angle Measurement: The collum angle was measured in degrees and is defined by the relationship between the crown and root of the tooth. The crown's longitudinal axis runs from the midpoint of the incisor's cutting edge to the centre of the crown at the cemento-enamel junction (CEJ). The root's longitudinal axis is drawn from the root apex to the midpoint between the facial and lingual surfaces at the CEJ. (Fig 1,2)

Fig.1 : Schematic representation of Collum angle

Fig.2 : Measurement of Collum angle on lateral cephalogram

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Data entry and analysis were performed using SPSS version 25 for Windows (SPSS, Inc.; Chicago, Illinois). The mean and standard deviation were calculated for quantitative variables like age and collum angle, while frequencies and percentages were used to represent qualitative data such as gender and patient profiles (high/low angle). The significance level for the study was set at 5%, and stratification techniques were employed to adjust and control for confounding factors like age and gender. A Student's t-test was conducted to compare the mean collum angle between the high and low angle patient profiles.

RESULTS:

A Pearson chi-square test was used to assess the association between gender and patient growth pattern, as shown in Table 1. No significant association was found between gender and growth patterns ($p=0.269$). The mean age was 18.44 ± 4.56 years for high-angle patients and 19.37 ± 4.20 years for low-angle patients, with no significant difference in age between the profiles ($p=0.417$). An independent-sample t-test was performed to compare the collum angle across patient profiles. The mean collum angle was 4.35 ± 1.49 for vertical growers and 2.41 ± 1.60 for horizontal growers, with a highly significant difference between the two profiles ($p=0.000$). The detailed mean difference of age and collum angle with respect to the growth pattern is presented in Table 2. The detailed mean difference of age and collum angle with respect to the growth pattern is presented in Table 3.

Table 1 : The association between gender and the growth pattern of patients

Gender	Growth pattern		p Value
	Vertical	Horizontal	
Male	27	25	0.269
Female	23	25	
Total	N= 50	N= 50	

Table 2 : The mean difference of age and collum angle with respect to the growth pattern

Characteristics	Growth Pattern		p value
	Vertical growers	Horizontal growers	
Age	18.88 ± 4.56	19.37 ± 4.20	0.417
Collum Angle	$4.35^\circ\pm 1.49^\circ$	$2.41^\circ\pm 1.60^\circ$	0.000

Table 3 : The mean difference of age and collum angle with respect to the gender

Characteristics	Gender		p value
	Male	Female	
Age	19.07 ± 4.53	18.79 ± 4.40	0.838
Collum Angle	$2.93^\circ\pm 1.97^\circ$	$3.66^\circ\pm 1.74^\circ$	0.188

DISCUSSION-

Achieving proper anterior torque in orthodontic brackets is crucial for obtaining normal overjet, overbite, good aesthetics, and an ideal dental relationship. Two key factors contribute to optimal tooth positioning when using pre-adjusted straight-wire appliances: the correct placement of brackets on the labial and buccal tooth surfaces to ensure accurate tip and torque, and the normal crown-root morphology. However, expressing the ideal torque can be challenging due to variations in tooth morphology, different wire materials, slot sizes, ligation methods, and the clinician's experience.⁹ Andrews' concept of pre-adjusted straight-wire appliances identified six essential elements for ideal occlusion,^{10,11} with the third key being correct crown inclination, assuming the collum angle (CA) for each tooth is zero.¹⁰ This assumption has been used frequently in lateral cephalometric analysis, though variations in crown and root morphology can limit the efficacy of the straight-wire system. These limitations are often overcome through bracket positioning and wire bending, depending on the clinician's expertise.

Numerous studies have discussed the formation of the collum angle, with maxillary central incisor bending being a primary cause. Backlund et al.¹² suggested that lower lip forces contribute to this bending, forming the collum angle. Other researchers have indicated that genetic and hereditary factors may also play a role in this phenomenon.^{4,13} The movement of anterior teeth is limited by alveolar bone thickness and vertical height, rather than root length.¹⁴ While tooth morphology is often overlooked, some studies emphasize its importance due to variations among different types of pre-adjusted bracket systems.¹⁵

Changes in treatment and mechanics, particularly torquing the root into the palatal cortex, can increase the risk of root resorption, as reported by Kaley and Phillips.¹⁶ For instance, in cases of extruded or protruded maxillary central incisors, intruding the tooth first moves the root apex into a wider area of cancellous bone, which is then followed by retraction and torquing mechanics. To overcome challenges related to intrusion, extrusion, and torquing, understanding the crown-root relationship in the bucco-lingual plane is essential.¹⁷

Bryant was the first to investigate the impact of incisor morphology variability on torque expression, identifying three morphological landmarks for the maxillary central incisor⁵: lingual crown curvature, labial surface angle, and the collum angle (or crown-to-root angulation). Subsequent studies have focused on the second and third features.^{7,9} Before the advent of cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT), lateral cephalometry was the primary

method for studying the labial surface angle and collum angle.^{4,7} Previous research has examined CA in sagittal malocclusions, both in Western and South-East Asian populations^{3,6,7}, but vertical skeletal malocclusion using lateral cephalograms has not been studied extensively, prompting the focus of this study.

Williams et al.¹⁸ measured the crown-root angles in all four classes of malocclusion, finding significant differences between Class II Division 1 and Division 2. Srinivasan et al.⁸ also measured the CA in Class II Division 2 patients, reporting averages of $5.3^{\circ} \pm 4.2^{\circ}$ for Class II Division 1 and $10.6^{\circ} \pm 4.4^{\circ}$ for Class II Division 2, noting that the lower lip line influences the difference. Bauer¹⁹ measured the CA in Class I and Class II Division 2 malocclusions, finding significantly higher values in the latter. Israr⁷ reported CA values of $3.65^{\circ} \pm 3.79^{\circ}$ for Class II Division 1 and $10.03^{\circ} \pm 4.37^{\circ}$ for Division 2, while Zahra²⁰ found increased CA in Class II Division 2 cases, with values of $5.12^{\circ} \pm 3.78^{\circ}$ for Class I, $6.09^{\circ} \pm 4.57^{\circ}$ for Class II Division 1, $15.02^{\circ} \pm 7.99^{\circ}$ for Division 2, and $6.94^{\circ} \pm 3.80^{\circ}$ for Class III.

In the present study, no significant difference in CA was found between males and females. However, we did observe a significant difference in the mean CA of maxillary central incisors between high-angle and low-angle cases, with high-angle cases showing an increased CA ($4.35^{\circ} \pm 1.49^{\circ}$) compared to low-angle cases ($2.41^{\circ} \pm 1.60^{\circ}$). This suggests that maxillary central incisor morphology plays a crucial role in factors like root resorption, dehiscence, fenestration, and torque variations, primarily due to root bending. Accurate assessment of crown-root morphology before bracket positioning is essential for orthodontic treatments.

Wang et al.³ measured the CA in various vertical malocclusions, reporting values of $0.94^{\circ} \pm 6.71^{\circ}$ for high-angle, $-1.02^{\circ} \pm 6.30^{\circ}$ for average, and $1.74^{\circ} \pm 5.28^{\circ}$ for low-angle cases, though the differences were not statistically significant. In contrast, our study found significant CA variations based on vertical measurements. Harris⁴ concluded that there was no correlation between CA and other vertical growth factors like lower face height, but our findings indicated a correlation, suggesting potential ethnic and racial influences on CA.

The study had some limitations, such as a small sample size. Future research could focus on comparing CA values across younger and older age groups to assess changes over time due to lip strain. Additionally, socioeconomic factors may also impact lip strain and influence results.

CONCLUSION:

The present study concluded that there is a highly significant difference in mean collum angle between vertical and horizontal growing patients.

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